

TRE Provider Forum Survey on Trusted Research Environments

Introduction to the survey

The survey takes approximately 30 minutes to complete in one sitting.

If an open ended question is not applicable to the environment in question, it can be skipped, but leaving a note about doing so is appreciated. Only some of the questions regarding administrative information are mandatory in the survey. If the provider in question is operating several environments, it is advisable to answer the survey for all of them separately.

This survey is based on a survey done previously by the HDRUK¹, and structured around the Five Safes², but it has been modified to suit the needs of the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

The survey is divided into six parts:

1. Administrative information
2. Safe Projects - Is the data being used appropriately?
3. Safe People - Who is going to be accessing the data?
4. Safe Data - How will the data be accessed?
5. Safe Settings - What computing/analytics services does the environment provide?
6. Safe Outputs - How do users export data from your environment?

Each part will have their own question pattern to be completed. Long answer boxes are provided for certain questions for you to specify your response. Please use them liberally. We appreciate you providing as much information as you can. Please also feel free to provide links whenever the requested information is available openly online.

Target audience

¹ <https://hdruk.github.io/TRE-Survey/>

² <https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/help/secure-lab/what-is-the-five-safes-framework/>

This survey is directed at EOSC-ENTRUST partner organizations who identify themselves as trusted research environment providers or are representing providers in the project. It is up to the providers to choose the most suitable individual experts to draft and submit the survey responses. We do not collect personal identifiers from the individuals submitting responses for this survey.

Premise/purpose of survey

One of the EOSC-ENTRUST project's tasks is to create an inventory of TREs operated by the TRE provider forum members. This survey serves the purpose of the inventory, as well as capability mapping and gap analysis. The aim is to also collect an initial set of high-level requirements and best practices on TREs from the provider forum members. In addition, the outcomes will give input for the TRE blueprint, to be developed by the work package on architecture. In the first phase this mapping will be conducted by collecting information solely from the project partners (and their affiliated organisations where relevant). The inventory will be updated twice during the project, which will allow adding new information categories and widening the scope of included providers and environments. The results of the survey will be available for EOSC-ENTRUST project partners on the project drive. A summary of the results will be presented at the second Requirements and Capabilities Workshop.

Use of answers

Answers will be used for the first iteration of the TRE inventory, one of EOSC-ENTRUST project milestones. In this first phase the inventory will be published internally within the project (by the end of M6). The information gathered will be stored in the EOSC-ENTRUST Google drive, where it is freely accessible to all registered project participants. The data will be managed and stored during the project and after the project according to the EOSC-ENTRUST project data management plan, consortium agreement, and other relevant project guidelines.

When responding, each provider must take into consideration their own information security and confidentiality requirements. All providers will have opportunities to update their information before the external publication of the second version of the TRE inventory (by the end of M18). Even then the survey results will not be published as such but will be collectively curated by the TRE provider forum participants.

What do we mean by TRE in the context of this survey?

For the purpose of this survey a trusted research environment (TRE) is any digital solution, or an interoperable collection of solutions, specifically intended for handling sensitive research data. There are other terms also in use for environments for handling sensitive data, such as secure processing environment (SPE) and data safe haven, etc. This survey is NOT intended only for those solutions that self-identify as TRE's. The aim is to collect information from all and any environments for handling sensitive data provided by the EOSC-ENTRUST project partners (and their close affiliates).

About EOSC-ENTRUST

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.

The project brings together providers of operational TREs from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language. This blueprint for interoperability is anchored in the EOSC Interoperability Framework spanning the four dimensions of legal, organisational, technical and semantic interoperability. EOSC-ENTRUST has identified four driver projects covering genomics, clinical trials, social science and public private partnerships to benchmark capabilities, inform blueprint design and demonstrate secure data analysis using federated workflows.

Contact person for the survey

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Questions

* Mandatory question

1. Administrative Information

Please feel free to provide links as responses whenever possible/relevant

1.1 Name of organisation hosting the environment*

1.2 Name of environment*

1.3 Primary term used to classify the environment*

- Trusted Research Environment (TRE)
- Safe Processing Environment (SPE)
- Data Safe Haven
- HPC
- Other:

1.4 Is the environment dedicated to handling sensitive data, or is it multi-purpose?*

- Just for handling sensitive data
- Available also for non-sensitive data use cases
- Other:

1.5 Public description of environment (please provide a link)*

1.6 Number of active end-users (handling sensitive data in the environment)

1.7 Number of active projects (handling sensitive data in the environment)

1.8 Anything you would like to add regarding administrative information?

2. Safe Projects - Is the data being used appropriately?

Please feel free to provide links as responses whenever possible/relevant

2.1 Is the organisation providing the environment also the data controller, or just a processor?

*Data controller = determines the **purposes** for which and the **means** by which sensitive data is processed*

*Data processor = processes sensitive data only **on behalf of the controller***

- The organization providing the environment is the data processor AND the data controller
- The organization providing the environment is ONLY a processor
- The organization providing the environment can be the data controller, or just the data processor, depending on the use case
- Other:

2.2 What multinational, national, regional, or local legal or other binding requirements do you as the environment provider need to comply with?

- GDPR
- EHDS
- NIS2
- ISO27001
- Other standards (please give details in open answer field)
- National/regional requirements (please give details in open answer field)
- Local (i.e. insitutional or otherwise pertaining to a limited group of actors) requirement (please give details in open answer field)
- Not applicable
- Don't know
- Other:

2.3 What type of project documentation is required from end-users/projects to be granted access to the environments?

- Research plan
- Lay summary of project
- Description of purpose for accessing the data
- Description of purpose for accessing and using the environment
- Data management plan
- Documentation on ethical review
- Documentation on need of computational capacity
- Documentation on legal compliance (please specify in open answer field)
- Information on project participants (i.e. environment end-users)
- Required documentation depends on the type of use (please specify below)
- Other:

Details on required documentation from end-users/projects:

2.4 Is public benefit a requirement for handling sensitive data in your environment? Please provide details below

- Yes
- No

Details on requirement of providing public benefit

2.5 Anything you would like to add regarding safe projects?

3. Safe People - Who is going to be accessing the data?

Please feel free to provide links as responses whenever possible/relevant

3.1 Does the environment have a list of defined roles? If there's a public listing available, please provide a link in the open answer ("other")

- Data controller
- Data access committee representative
- Data custodian
- Data consumer
- Connector
- Principia investigator
- Project manager
- Project vice-manager
- Project
- Other:

3.2 How do you manage and regulate the individuals who access and use your environment?

3.3 What technical access mechanisms you support?

- Self-service user login
- Single Sign On (SSO)
- Two-factor authentication (2FA)
- Don't know
- Other:

3.4 Do you require users (or their organizations) to comply to minimum level of system requirements to access your environment? If yes, please specify in the open answer

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

If you answered "yes" to the previous question, please write specifications here.

3.5 Does access to the environment have to be via a recognised "trusted" organisation or network? (if yes, please specify below)

- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- In some cases (please specify below)

If you answered "yes" or "in some cases" to the previous question, please write specifications here.

3.6 Can the environment be accessed internationally? Please specify below.
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- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Please write specifications to the previous question here.

3.7 Anything you would like to add regarding safe people?

4. Safe Data - How will the data be accessed?

Please feel free to provide links as responses whenever possible/relevant.

If an open ended question is not relevant for /applicable to your environment, please respond "doesn't apply", and move on to the next question.

4.1 How do you manage datasets for users within your environment? Please provide details.

4.2 How do you provision external datasets (datasets not permanently hosted by your organisation) into your environment? Please provide details.

4.3 Does the environment only handle particular types of data? Please specify

4.4 What data types can a user import to your environment?

4.5 Do you provide record linkage services? If so please provide details

4.6 Which tools, techniques and processes do you use in your environment to manage and reduce the potential risk of re-identification?

4.7 Describe your process for avoiding safety breaches on data inputs

4.8 Are there certified data paths in the TRE? Please specify below

- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- Not applicable

Details on certified data paths

4.9 Anything you would like to add regarding safe data?

5. Safe Settings - What computing/analytics services does the environment provide?

Please feel free to provide links as responses whenever possible/relevant.

If an open ended question is not relevant for /applicable to your environment, please respond "doesn't apply", and move on to the next question.

If you find a question redundant, and something you have already addressed in a previous question, please feel free to skip that question (if open answer available, preferably with a note that information has already been given).

5.1. Environment administration

5.1.1 Is your environment provisioned on premise/private cloud, public cloud or a hybrid approach? Please provide details

- On premise
- Private cloud
- Public cloud (third party provider)
- Hybrid

Please provide the details for the previous question here

5.1.2 Which security audits and certifications have been completed for your environment?

5.1.3 Do you provide tenancy isolation between projects/users?

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- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- Other:

5.1.4 What security measures are in place to mitigate the risk of a. unauthorized access, b. data loss, c. misuse by user?

a. Security measures for mitigating unauthorized access

b. Security measures for mitigating data loss

c. Security measures for mitigating misuse by users

5.2. Infrastructure details

5.2.1 Does your environment have a defined charging structure? If so, please provide details

5.2.2 Do you provide access to high performance computing (HPC) in/through your environment? Please give details below

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Details on providing HPC in/through the environment

5.2.3 What is the standard/maximum computing power you can offer to users of your environment?

5.2.4 Do you have standard base operating system? If so, please provide details including any modifications

5.2.5 Are users allowed to modify the base Virtual Machine (VM)? If so, please provide details on how this is managed

5.2.6 Do you provide users direct access to a Virtual Machine in your environment? Please provide details.

5.2.7 What measures do you employ to control access to the Virtual Machine?

5.2.7 Do you support analytical workflows that require more than a single virtual machine?

- Genome Wide Association Studies
- Computational fluid dynamics
- Deep learning
- No, we don't support analytical workflows requiring more then single VM
- Other:

5.3. Software details

5.3.1 What software is provided as default to users? Please provide details

5.3.2 Are users allowed to import code/software (including libraries) into their environment? if so, do you employ any security measures during import? Please provide details

5.3.3 Does your environment provide managed internal collaboration tooling (i.e. tools that facilitate communication, project management, file sharing, adn other collaborative activities between project members)? If so, please provide details

5.3.4 What measures do you have in place to detect/prevent malicious code execution in your environment?

5.4. Managed services details

5.4.1 Does your environment provide managed data analytics services? If so, please provide details

5.4.2 Does your environment support federated queries of metadata and or data from external authorised users? If so, please provide details.

5.4.3 Does your environment support federated analytics? If so please provide details.

5.4.4 Do you provide support for use or development of artificial intelligence / machine learning? If yes, please provide details

5.5. Other

5.5.1 Do you have plans for next generation capabilities?

5.5.2 Do you have a reference architecture you follow? If yes, please specify (and provide a web link if available)

5.6 Anything you would like to add regarding safe settings?

6. Safe Outputs - How do users export data from your environment?

6.1 What types of data can a user export from your environment?

- Plain text files
- Document files
- Spreadsheet files
- Source code
- Images
- Other:

6.2 Do you have plans to support export of other data types?

6.3 Describe your process for checking disclosure control on outputs

6.4 Do you publish information on the projects using the environment?

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- Yes
- No

- Don't know
- Other:

6.5 Anything you would like to add regarding safe outputs?